

The life of Nathaniel Hawthorne

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Annotatsiya : Mazkur maqolada ingliz yozuvchilaring eng mahoratli namoyondalaridan biri hisoblangan N. Hovsorning (Nathaniel Hawthorne) shaxsiy hayot yo'li , oilaviy ahvoli, ta'lim olgan joylari , ilk bor yozgan asari va undan keying ijod namunalari haqida so'z yuritiladi.Hayotida sodir bo'lgan har bir jarayon uning haqiqiy yozuvchi bo'lib yetishishida muhim rol o'ynagan.

Kalit so'zlar: atrof -muhit, hissa qo'shish, yozuvchi , tajriba

Abstract:The represented article deal with the personal life of Nathaniel Hawthorne who is considered one of the most skilled representatives of English writers, his family situation, places of education, his first work and later works. What happened in his life each process played an important role in his development as a true writer.

Key words:environment, contribution, writer, experience

Born on July 4, 1804, Nathaniel Hawthorne was the best son of Captain Nathaniel Hawthorne and Elizabeth Clark Manning Hawthorne. (Hawthorne added a "w" to his name after graduating from college.) After Captain Hawthorne's lack of existence in 1808, Nathaniel, his mother, and his sisters have been forced to move in with the Mannings, are relatives of Mrs. Hawthorne. they had been Here Nathaniel Hawthorne grew up in a circle of ladies and now no longer the use of a sturdy male role models; this environment may have contributed to what biographers call his shyness and introverted personality.

In 1821, Hawthorne enrolled at Bowdoin College in Brunswick, Maine. Among his classmates have been Henry Wadsworth Longfellow, the well-known poet and destiny Harvard professor, and Franklin Pierce, the destiny 14th President of the United States. Another classmate, Horatio Bridge, later provided to assure Hawthorne towards loss if he posted Hawthorne's first series of brief tales to a writer in Boston. Hawthorne graduated with inside the center of his elegance in 1825. Of his ambitions, he wrote: "I do now no longer need to be a physician and stay with men's diseases, or minister with their sins, or stay with their quarrels. , I see not anything left for me however to be an author."

This duration of Hawthorne's existence end up mixed with the joys of have a take a observe and the resentment of financial dependence. Although he studied with the famous lexicographer Joseph E. Worcester at an early age, he did now not like college much. An harm saved him at home for a year while he became nine, and his first "friends" had been books through manner of manner of Shakespeare, Spenser, Bunyan, and 18th-century novelist .During this time, Mrs. Hawthorne moved her very own family to land owned thru manner of way of the Mannings near Raymond, Maine. Nathaniel's fondest recollections of nowadays are: "I ran very wild, and with the resource of the use of this time I may want to have run wild at will, fished all day, or shot with the antique fowl." This idle existence withinside the desert held its charms for the boy's imagination, but it brought about 1819 whilst he lower back to Salem and spent years getting equipped for college.

For the following 12 years, Hawthorne lived in relative isolation in an upstairs room in his mother's house, in which he labored on enhancing his writing skills. He additionally commenced maintaining notebooks or journals, a dependancy that endured for the duration of his life. He regularly recorded thoughts and descriptions,

and his phrases at the moment are a wealthy supply of records approximately his themes, thoughts, methodological experiences, and subjects.

In 1828, he posted his first novel "Fanshaw": A Tale" at his personal expense. Then he finishes writing his maximum well-known work. The novel become so powerfully written that Hawthorne, displeased with the novel, attempted to shop for up all of the copies in order that nobody might study it. After that, he did now no longer submit any other novel for 25 years. By 1838, he had written two-thirds of the quick tales he changed into to write down in his lifetime. None of those testimonies attracted lots interest to him, and it changed into now no longer till 1837 that he supported the e-book of his university pal Horatio Bridge Hawthorne's series of Tales Twice Told. couldn't hobby the publisher. one by one in magazines. His classmate and pal Longfellow reviewed there book with sparkling words. Not handiest did Edgar Allan Poe, acknowledged for his admirable critiques of writers, write warmly of Hawthorne's book, he additionally took the possibility to perceive the quick tale in his now well-known review. Twice Told Tales is taken into consideration a masterpiece of literature and includes unmistakably American memories.

In 1838, Hawthorne met Sophia Amelia Peabody. He goes to great lengths to find his love, and the following year they get engaged. It was at this time that Hawthorne invested a thousand dollars of his meager capital in the community of Brook Farm in West Roxbury. There he met Ralph Waldo Emerson and the naturalist Henry David Thoreau. These transcendentalist thinkers greatly influenced Hawthorne's thinking about the importance of intuition rather than intellect in discovering the truths of nature and man. Hawthorne left the experiment in November 1841, disillusioned with society's attitude, tired of work, and with no hope

of financially supporting his wife. However, from this experience he created the setting for his next novel, *The Blithedale Romance*.

He needed to go away Brook Farm. He then traveled to Boston. During his ride to Boston, Hawthorne negotiated a revenue for destiny contributions to the *Democratic Review*. He and Sophia had been married in Boston on July 9, 1842, and that they moved collectively to Concord, Massachusetts. they lived for some time withinside the now famous " Old Manse .Hawthorne's lifestyles in the "Old Manse" changed into the happiest and maximum effective years of his existence, and those years introduced extraordinary achievements to his lifestyles. He changed into newly married, in love together along with his wife, and the encompassing surroundings changed into very fine for him, surrounded through many main literary figures of the time: Ralph Waldo Emerson, Henry David Thoreau, Margaret Fuller and Bronson Alcott. During this time, Hawthorne wrote for the *Democratic Review* and created a few stories to be posted in *Mosses from an Old Manse* in 1846.

Family concerns stored him far from his paintings for a few time. In fact, at some point of those years, Hawthorne needed to write the best prose works of his lifestyles. But those issues in his lifestyles gave him little or no possibility to create. But those problems in his existence did now no longer prevent Hawthorne from creating. In 1849, Hawthorne became capable of write his well-known paintings "The Scarlet .

In 1849, the own circle of relatives moved to Lennox, Massachusetts, in which Hawthorne met a brand new precise friend, the younger author Herman Melville. Melville turned into one of the younger writers who cherished literature. Melville felt fortunate to fulfill Hawthorne. Hawthorne additionally noticed Melville as his student.He stimulated the younger Melville, who later committed his ee-e book

Moby Dick to him and thanked him. During this duration - the length of "The Little Red House" in Lennox - Hawthorne wrote "The House of Seven Gables" and a few minor works, which had been posted in 1851.

Around the time Nathaniel and Sophia's second daughter, Rose, turned into born, the own circle of relatives moved to West Newton, wherein Hawthorne wrote a number of the maximum specific works of his career. There she finished and posted The Blithedale Romance, a unique approximately her reviews at Brooke's Farm, in addition to The Miracle Book for Girls and Boys. Children's literature changed into now no longer evolved at that time. Few writers wrote works for children. Since there has been very little kid's literature posted, Hawthorne's ee-e book became precise on this field. Hawthorn lived in nearly each city. He later went to Concord, in which he searched for a everlasting domestic for himself and his own circle of relatives. Hawthorne additionally had suitable friendships with girls writers. One of them become Louisa May Alcott, one of the well-known writers of that time.

In Concord, the Hawthorns discovered a everlasting domestic and acquired 9 acres of land from Bronson Alcott, Transcendentalist creator and Louisa May Alcott's father. After Hawthorne sold the house, he renamed it The Wayside, and in May 1852, he and his own circle of relatives moved in. After stepping into the brand new house, he had nearly no time to jot down, however Hawthorne did. in which he became to put in writing most effective works: Tanglewood Tales, every other series aimed toward younger readers, and The Life of Pierce, a campaign. autobiography for an antique university friend. As a end result of the biography, President Pierce commemorated Hawthorne with an appointment as United States Consul in Liverpool, England. The Hawthornes spent the subsequent seven years in Europe. Although Hawthorne wrote no extra fiction even as serving as consul, he stored a

magazine that later served as a supply of cloth for *Our Old Home*, a set of sketches handling English scenery, life, and manners posted in 1863. While in Italy, Hawthorne saved a pocket book that furnished cloth for his final, entire paintings of fiction, which turned into posted in England as *Transformation* and, in America, as *The Marble Faun*.

By the autumn of 1863, Hawthorne had grow to be ill. In an attempt to enhance his health, he and his exceptional pal and classmate Pierce traveled to New Hampshire in May 1864. But this experience became his closing experience. The creator who spent his lifestyles travelling met his loss of life at the same time as travelling. During this ride, he died in his sleep in Plymouth, New Hampshire on May 19 , 1864. He turned into buried in Sleepy Hollow Cemetery in Concord. And that is how the first-rate creator surpassed away. Not most effective all his colleagues, however all of the those who knew him withinside the metropolis got here to his funeral to honor him. Its bearers protected Longfellow, Holmes, Lowell, and Emerson.

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